

Affected tillers. The arrow points to leaves that have remained in the vegetative stage CRR1, India.

large numbers of nematodes inside the spikelets. No such nematodes were observed in affected tillers that remained in the vegetative stage. The primordial portions of affected tillers had one larva each of some insects. That symptom was not observed in gall midge-resistant varieties such as Ptb21 and Ptb18.

Differences in varietal reaction to this malformation, as well as its cause, are being investigated. ■

Influence of nitrogen fertilization on development of sheath blight

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Sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is severe in several rice-growing districts of Tamil Nadu. A pot-culture experiment was carried out to determine the effect of nitrogen (N) fertilizer on disease development. Three plants of ADT31, which is susceptible to sheath blight, were raised in concrete pots in kuruvai (Jun-Sep). Levels of 0, 49, 99, 148, 198, and 247 kg N/ha

Effect of nitrogen on the incidence of sheath blight disease.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Mean disease index (%)	Increase (%) over control	Mean grain yield (g/pot)	Increase (+) or decrease (-) (%) over control
0	41	—	10.4	—
49	52	25	16.3	+56.7
99	62	52	14.5	+39.9
148	14	80	12.2	+16.8
198	83	103		10.8 + 4.0
241	88	113		10.2 - 1.9

^aDisease: SE = 0.8746, CD = 2.64. Grain yield: SE = 0.6801, CD = 2.05. Significant at 1% level.

(converted from kg/acre) were calculated and applied with urea. At all N levels, 62 kg P/ha as superphosphate and 62 kg K/ha as muriate of potash were applied. Half of the N was applied as basal, along with the P and K; and the remaining half was topdressed 25 days after transplanting. At the maximum-tillering phase, the crop was inoculated

with the pathogen by the straw-bit method developed by Venkata Rao and Kannaiyan in 1973. The intensity of disease development was recorded using the Standard Evaluation System. Increased N level proportionately increased disease incidence (see table). Severe disease incidence at higher N levels reduced the grain yield considerably. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in Orissa, India

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During 1977–78 kharif, a rice disease was observed, especially in late-planted rice, in the experimental fields of the Regional Research Station of Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima.

Diseased plants were stunted and leaves became ragged and serrated. Vein-swelling was marked on the outer surface of the leaf sheath. Flag leaves were small, twisted, and malformed. Panicle emergence was often incomplete and panicles bore mostly empty grains. Most of the tillers of the diseased plants were branched and produced many panicles. Flowering in diseased plants was delayed. Symptoms in the ratoons were similar.

Because the above symptoms are similar to those of rice ragged stunt disease, reported and described by K. C. Ling (IRRN 2(5):6–7, 1977), the disease is suspected to be ragged stunt, reported for the first time in Orissa.

Field observations on percentage of hills infected and percentage of tillers showing malformation and twisted leaves among 73 rice varieties from the

National Screening Nursery were conducted in 1978 kharif. Infected hills varied from 0 to 90% among varieties; malformed tillers, from 0 to 61%. Highly infected varieties included RP884-33-6, OR34-21, OR27-7, IET1444, Benibhog, IR28, and Cauvery. IR36, Pankaja, OR117-4, and ADT31 showed no disease incidence. Transmission studies to confirm the disease are in progress. ■

Chemical control of sheath rot disease of rice

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae* is becoming serious in several high yielding rice cultivars. A pot-culture experiment on chemical control of sheath rot was conducted in pishanam (Jan-Apr) 1978, using the susceptible variety IR20. Eight fungicides – Hinosan EC, Kitazin EC, Benlate, Bavistin, Difolatan, Miltox, N.F. 48, and Daconil – at 0.2% concentrations were sprayed on the plants twice at 10-day intervals during the flowering stage. The disease incidence was recorded during harvest with the use of the 1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.